

ENCOMRAN Data Report - Assessing the interaction within EU food and feed risk analysis processes

Axel Menning¹, Joao Borges², Leonie Dendler¹, Ine van der Fels-Klerx², Mats Gunnar Andersson³

1 German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Max-Dohrn-Straße 8-10, 10589 Berlin, Germany

2 Wageningen University, Hollandseweg 1, 6706 KN, Wageningen, The Netherlands

3 National Veterinary Institute (SVA), Ulls Väg 2, SE751 82, Uppsala, Sweden

Content

1. Introduction	2
2. Methods.....	2
2.1 Online questionnaire	2
2.2 Sampling	6
2.3 Outcome variables	6
2.4 Statistical analyses.....	7
3. Results	8
3.1 Descriptive statistics.....	8
3.1.1 Background Questions.....	8
3.1.2 General Questions on Last Risk Analysis.....	11
3.1.3 Preparation of the last risk analysis	15
3.1.4 Execution of the last risk analysis	17
3.1.5 Reflections on the last risk analysis process	22
3.1.6 Challenges of risk analysis	26
3.2 Chi-squares and Kruskal-Wallis H tests.....	27
3.3 Correlations.....	27
4. Interpretation and concluding comments	28
General findings	30
Findings regarding the execution of risk analysis	30
Findings regarding the reflection on risk analysis	31
Conclusion.....	31

References	31
Appendix.....	32
A: Insights into type “Both”	32

1. Introduction

This report was created within the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) financed ENCOMRAN (ENhanced COMmunication in Risk ANalysis) (2021-2023) project. The objective of ENCOMRAN is to analyze and enhance communication and overall interaction between risk assessors and risk managers, thus facilitating the risk analysis process regarding food and feed hazards.

This report is the outcome of the data collection and analysis tasks of a survey conducted with risk assessors (RA) and risk managers (RM) in the European Union (EU). It captures and summarizes the interaction within EU food and feed risk analysis processes as it is perceived by risk managers and risk assessors. Herein risk analysis is understood as an interconnected process, composed of risk assessment, risk management and risk communication¹ (General food law, art. 3(10)).

2. Methods

2.1 Online questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed based on different sources of input. It contains questions that were developed and tested in the preceding project “ComRisk” (Andersson 2020). Further questions were added to qualify the interaction between risk assessment and risk management, based on literature related to risk governance, risk organization and public administration, in particular the cooperation, coordination, collaboration framework developed by McNamara (2012). Additional questions also emerged during continuous discussions within the ENCOMRAN consortium, which consists of practitioners from risk assessment, risk management and risk communication.

Early versions of the questionnaire were presented and discussed within subgroups as well as the whole consortium. Refined versions of the questionnaire were

¹ Regarding the definition of risk assessment and risk management and risk communication, we refer to the EFSA Glossary (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary>).

pre-tested with external risk managers and risk assessors. Based on the feedback, the wording of some questions was changed, and questions were removed in order to realize a total response time of around 45 minutes. The most substantial change based on the pre-test was to shift the focus of the questionnaire to the participant's last risk analysis instead of referring to the general risk analysis process. This was done to resolve the difficulty in providing summarized responses. The limitation of this change is that the questionnaire has to be handled as a probe into the last risk analysis of many risk analysts. With that, it provides insights into a certain period in time (first half of 2022) rather than the risk analysis process as a whole. The questionnaire contains closed questions (scales, single choice, and multiple choice) and open questions. Responses to open questions are excluded from this report for privacy reasons. Each question included the option to opt for "I don't know / I prefer not to say" except for one key question in the beginning, where not answering would result in exclusion from the questionnaire.

Prior to the questionnaire, an introductory text was provided as well as a form in which participants were asked for consent regarding voluntary participation and data privacy.

The questionnaire was divided into background questions, questions regarding the last risk analysis (general, preparation, execution, and reflection), and general challenges and improvements. See figure 1 for an overview.

Fig. 1, Structure of the Questionnaire.

The background questions were used to identify the risk analysis work performed by the participant (only in risk assessment, only in risk management, or both), and the parts of the risk analysis process in which the participant's organization was involved in (only provides risk assessment, only provides risk management, and provides both). For analysis, a distinction between "Risk Assessment" (RA), "Risk Management" (RM), and "Both" was made. Filters were applied depending on the participant's answers to these questions and the questions regarding the last risk analysis thereafter were type-specific (risk assessment, risk management, both).

Except for minor changes, such as replacing "risk assessment" with "risk management", the questions were largely the same and comparable for risk assessment and risk management. The block of questions for the type "both" was shorter since many questions regarding the interaction would not have been meaningful.

The general part of the questionnaire included a series of questions used to assess general characteristics of the participant's last risk analysis. For this report, we focus on questions that assess the subject area, the length, the autonomy, and shared resources of the last risk analysis in which the participant was involved in.

The preparation part included a series of questions used to analyze how the last risk analysis was prepared. The execution part included a series of questions used to assess how the last risk analysis was executed. The reflection part included a series of questions used to measure the participant's reflection on the last risk analysis.

The part *challenges and improvements* were the same for all participants. It is specifically meant to narrow down interaction and communication issues during risk analysis, which will be addressed by a guidance document (ENCOMRAN outcome). The majority of the questions in this part were open questions to allow respondents to describe unique situations that may cause or resolve issues. For this report, we focus on five statements used to measure the frequency of communication challenges. Participants indicated the frequency of each communication challenge using a five-point scale (1 = never, 2 = rarely, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, and 5 = always).

The 2nd part of background questions included demographic characteristics: gender (female, male), age (measured in years), and experience in risk analysis (measured in years), and country of work (for data privacy reason, country data are not used in the analysis).

For the present report, only the analysis of the most relevant questions are described. The full questionnaire is available as annex.

2.2 Sampling

The population of interest consisted of risk assessors and risk managers working in risk analysis regarding feed and food hazards in European countries. Contact details of risk assessors and risk managers were collected via EFSA focal points and the heads of agencies mailing list. An invitational email with an anonymized link for the online survey among was circulated. Two follow-up reminders and personal invitations of relevant persons were made to assure a good circulation of the survey. Respondent data were collected in the period 1 July to 30 September 2022. An informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to participating in this research.

While an initial sample of 120 participants completed the online questionnaire, only 79.2 % of the questionnaires contained sufficient data to be included in the analyses. Therefore, the final sample is composed of 95 participants. The average age of the respondents was 50 years, the average experience was 14 years, there were 48.3% females, 44.0 % males, and 7.7% prefer not to say the gender.

2.3 Outcome variables

Several outcome variables for the risk analysis process were included in the questionnaire design. Complete questions can be found in the questionnaire (annex) along with a short title in brackets for guidance. These variables are:

- Satisfaction with communication (RALR2, RMLR2)
- Quality of risk analysis process (RALR1, RMLR1, BLR2)
- Relationship / trust among involved actors (RALR4, RMLR4)

Quality and relationship / trust were measured based on one respondent's mean values of several subdimensions.

Quality consists of the subdimensions:

- Work process
- Transparency
- Effectiveness
- Efficiency
- Openness
- Flexibility

- Time management
- Timeliness

Relationship / Trust consists of the subdimensions:

- Familiarity
- Vulnerability_a
- Vulnerability_b
- Vulnerability_c
- Feeling_valued
- Ability
- Interest_alignment

All outcome variables / subdimensions of aggregated outcome variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale and presented as such.

2.4 Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses were performed in four steps. First, descriptive statistics were used to explore the main features of the variables.

Second, we used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between RA and RM for the following variables: the length of the last risk analysis, and the autonomy. We also used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between those who shared resources and those who did not share resources in the last risk analysis for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. Finally, we used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between those who received feedback and those who did not receive it in the last risk analysis for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Third, we used the Kruskal-Wallis H test to determine differences among RA, RM, and those who do both for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. We also used the Kruskal-Wallis H test to determine differences among participants working in organizations providing risk assessment, providing risk management, and providing both for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. Finally, we used the Kruskal-

Wallis H to determine differences between those that indicated that trust was not necessary on the last risk analysis and those who indicated that trust was crucial, and those who indicated that trust was only necessary at a higher level, not at a working level for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Fourth, correlation between relevant variables and outcome variables were calculated using Pearson's or Spearman's correlation coefficient.

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive statistics

In this section we provide an overview for the most relevant descriptive statistics.

Further analysis of the results can be done by working with the data set, provided as annex. The following remarks provide help to navigate through the descriptive statistics section.

- If not indicated with [MC] for multiple choice the questions were single choice questions.
- If not indicated with [R] for randomized, the items had been displayed in the same order.
- For each question, the nomenclature (e.g., LG1) is provided, which helps to identify the entire question in the ENCOMRAN questionnaire (annex).
- Risk Assessment is abbreviated with RA, Risk Management with RM

3.1.1 Background Questions

Type of risk analysis

The sample was composed mostly of RA (49.5%), and by people working in organizations that provide both risk assessment and risk management (49.5%) (See Table 1 and Table 2).

Table 1 – Type of work, BG1 (n=95).

Type of work	Frequency	%
Both	27	28.4
Only RA	47	49.5

Only RM	21	22.1
---------	----	------

Table 2 – Type of organization work, BG2a (n=95).

Type of work	Frequency	%
Only RA	28	29.5
Only RM	20	21.0
Both	47	49.5

Furthermore, the organizations which participate in risk analysis can be distinguished between those who either perform risk assessment or risk management (fully separated) and those who are involved in both risk assessment and risk management, either in different departments or in the same department (by different persons), or organizations in which individuals perform both risk assessment and risk management.

Table 3 – Organizational structure, BG2a & BG2b (n=94).

Organizational structure	Frequency	%
Fully separated	48	51.1
Different department	37	39.4
Same department	7	7.5
Same person	2	2.1

For further analysis we define Risk Assessors, Risk Managers and the Type “Both” as follows.

Table 4 – Definition of RA, RM and Both

Risk Assessment	<p>Question BG1: “How would you describe your work within the risk analysis process?”</p> <p>Answer: “I work ... only in risk assessment.”</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Question BLG1: “In this particular instance [last Risk Analysis you were involved with], did you...”,</p>
------------------------	---

	Answer: "... only provide the risk assessment, while the risk management was handled by someone else."
Risk Management	<p>Question BG1: "How would you describe your work within the risk analysis process?"</p> <p>Answer: "I work ... only in risk management."</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Question BLG1: "In this particular instance [last Risk Analysis you were involved with], did you..."</p> <p>Answer: "... only provide the risk management, while the risk assessment was handled by someone else."</p>
Both	<p>Question BG1: "How would you describe your work within the risk analysis process?"</p> <p>Answer: "I work ...both in risk assessment and in risk management."</p> <p>AND</p> <p>Question BLG1: "In this particular instance [last Risk Analysis you were involved with], did you..."</p> <p>Answer: "provide both risk assessment and risk management."</p>

Table 5 – Risk Assessment, Risk Management, Both as defined above, BG1 and BLG1 (n=95).

Type of work	Frequency	%
Only RA	55	57,9
Only RM	31	32.6
Both	9	9.5

As explained above, for those participants who responded that their type of work was both risk assessment and risk management, we further asked them whether in their last risk analysis, they performed the role of RA or RM. Based on their answers, they were then considered RA or RM for the subsequent analysis. As such, the number of RA and RM in the next Tables increased compared to Table 1. Besides, some participants chose not to answer all questions, or marked the option "I do not know/I prefer not to say". Therefore, there is missing and/or incomplete data in some instances. For

transparency, the sample size is provided between brackets in all Tables. For those interested in the type “Both”, we refer to Appendix A.

Experience in the field of food safety

Furthermore, the work experience in the field of food safety was assessed throughout the whole sample.

Table 6 – Work Experience in the field of food safety, BG4.

summary	All (n=95)	RA (n=55)	RM (n=31)	Both (n=9)
Min.	0.0	1.0	0.0	2.0
1st Qu.	6.0	10.0	5.0	8.0
Median	15.0	15.0	9.0	15.0
Mean	13.9	14.91	11.48	16.6
3rd Qu.	20.0	20.00	15.0	25.0
Max.	40.0	40.00	35.0	33.0
NA's	6	2	2	2

3.1.2 General Questions on Last Risk Analysis

Subject area of the last risk analysis

Most of the RA and RM provided their last risk analysis either in the subject area of “only biological hazards in food” or in “only chemical hazards in food” (See Table 7).

Table 7 – Subject area of the last risk analysis, LG1 (n=55). [MC]

Subject Area	RA (n=55)	RM (n=31)
Biological hazards in drinking water.	1	
Biological hazards in feed.	3	2
Biological hazards in food.	22	8
Biological hazards in water to animals.	2	
Chemical hazards in drinking water.	3	3
Chemical hazards in feed.	4	4

Chemical hazards in food.	31	13
Chemical hazards in water to animals.	2	1
Emerging risks (related to food or feed).	5	3
Other (please specify):	5	7
Physical hazards in feed.	1	1
Physical hazards in food.	1	3

Category of last risk analysis

Most of the RA provided their last risk analysis in the category of “routine risk assessment” (56.4%) while most of the RM provided it in the category of “rapid risk assessment” (37.9%) (See Table 8).

Table 8 – Categories of the last risk analysis, LG2.

Category	RA (n=55)	RM (n=29)
Expert opinion, i.e., a summary of evidence-based views given by experts in the field (often used when there is a lack of data).	9 (16.4%)	6 (20.7%)
Rapid risk assessment, i.e., a risk assessment based on limited data due to time constraints (often used in initial stages of an event or after an incident of potential public health concern).	12 (21.8%)	11 (37.9%)
Routine risk assessment, i.e., a systematic review of all available scientific data to evaluate the magnitude of risks associated with certain hazards.	31 (56.4%)	9 (31.0%)
Other:	3 (5.4%)	3 (10.3%)

Length of risk analysis process

Regarding the length of the last risk analysis, most of the sample provided it in less than a month (See Table 9). Notably, 18.2% of RA and 14.3% of RM reported that their last risk analysis took more than a year.

Table 9 – Length of the last risk analysis, LG3.

Length	RA (n=55)	RM (n=28)
Less than a month	18 (32.7%)	16 (57.1%)
One to three months	11 (20.0%)	5 (17.9%)
Four to six months	11 (20.0%)	2 (7.1%)
Seven to twelve months	5 (9.1%)	1 (3.6%)
More than a year	10 (18.2%)	4 (14.3%)

Autonomy during last risk analysis

Most of the RA indicated that their last risk analysis was performed fully autonomously (72.2%), while only 24.1% of the RM indicated to work fully autonomously in their last risk analysis (See Table 10).

Table 10 – Autonomy during the last risk analysis, LG7.

Autonomy	RA (n=54)	RM (n=29)
A coordinating entity from another organization coordinated the risk analysis process.	2 (3.7%)	2 (6.9%)
A coordinating entity from my own organization coordinated the risk analysis process.	5 (9.3%)	10 (34.5%)
I worked jointly with risk management.	6 (11.1%)	7 (24.1%)
The risk assessment was performed fully autonomously.	39 (72.2%)	7 (24.1%)
Other	2 (3.7%)	3 (10.3%)

Based on the Risk Governance Model (IRGC, 2017) a more granular view on the distribution of risk analysis tasks has been retrieved.

Table 11 – Involvement in Risk Governance Tasks [MC], LG4

Tasks	RA (n=55)	RM (n=31)
Screening and early warning.	12	7
Problem framing.	22	8
Determining how to assess the risk.	34	4
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	12	8
Hazard identification.	33	4
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	39	2
Hazard characterization.	36	4
Risk characterization.	43	3
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	3	
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	1	1
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	1	
Compiling risk profiles.	7	1
Knowledge characterization (e.g., in terms of uncertainty; complexity; ambiguity).	24	2
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	9	7
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	13	9
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	11	9
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	1	10
Planning options to deal with the risk.	2	6
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	0	8
Controlling the implemented options.	1	7
Evaluating the implemented options.	2	3
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	1	3
Risk communication.	13	12
Stakeholder engagement.	6	10
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	1	3

The majority of RA and RM indicated that they did not share resources with their counterparts in the last risk analysis (See Table 12).

Table 12 – Shared resources, LG8a.

Shared resources	No (%)	Yes (%)
RA (n=52)	92.3	7.7
RM (n=28)	60.7	39.3

3.1.3 Preparation of the last risk analysis

Questions regarding the last risk assessment mandate

An essential part of the information sharing between RA and RM is information regarding the risk assessment mandate. The following Tables provide insights into the development of the mandate, what kind of information was included into the mandate and how comprehensible the mandate was for RA. Most of the RA indicated that the last risk assessment mandate was formulated by RM alone (35.2%) while most of the RM reported that it was jointly formulated by RA and RM (43.5%) (See Table 13).

Table 13 – Formulation of the last risk assessment mandate, LP1.

Formulation	RA (n=54)	RM (n=23)
It was formulated by risk management alone.	19 (35.2%)	8 (34.8%)
It was formulated mainly by risk management, but with some input from risk assessment.	13 (24.1%)	5 (21.4%)
Risk assessment and risk management formulated the risk assessment mandate in a joint process.	11 (20.4%)	10 (43.5%)
In another way (please specify):	6 (11.1%)	3 (9.7%)
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	5 (9.3%)	5 (16.1%)

Regarding the information included in the last risk assessment mandate, “a description of the risk to be assessed” was most frequently cited by RA and RM in the sample, sometimes with other information (See Table 14).

Table 14 – Information included in the last risk assessment mandate, LP2. [MC].

Information	RA (n=54)	RM (n=31)
A description of the circumstance that gave rise to the enquiry.	27	13
A description of the risk to be assessed.	45	17
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	1	5
Information on different risk management strategies pertaining to this risk.	8	5
Other (please specify):	2	1
The intended use of the risk assessment.	27	9

Table 15 – Comprehensibility of the mandate (scale 1 "do not agree at all" – 5 "Agree completely"), RALP4. [R]

Question	1	2	3	4	5
The risk assessment mandate was written in an understandable way. (n=54)	3 (6.0%)	2 (4.0%)	6 (12.0%)	15 (30.0%)	24 (48.0%)
The mandate defined the risk to be assessed precisely and clearly. (n=54)	3 (5.9%)	6 (11.8%)	5 (9.8%)	14 (27.5%)	23 (45.1%)
The mandate clearly stated the purpose for which the assessment was needed. (n=54)	2 (3.9%)	2 (3.9%)	6 (11.8%)	15 (29.4%)	26 (51.0%)
I had problems understanding what exactly was expected from my risk assessment. (n=54)	29 (55.8%)	13 (25.0%)	4 (7.7%)	5 (9.6%)	1 (1.9%)
I had difficulties understanding some of the technical terms used in the risk assessment mandate. (n=54)	36 (69.2%)	6 (11.5%)	4 (7.7%)	4 (7.7%)	2 (3.8%)

3.1.4 Execution of the last risk analysis

Communication

The initial question on communication between RA and RM was about the frequency of communication on a scale from 1 to 100. The input was realized with a slider that had a starting position at 50.

Table 16 – Frequency of communication, LE3a.

summary	RA (n=49)	RM (n=28)
Min.	-1.0	-1.0
1st Qu.	10.0	15.5
Median	30.0	50.0
Mean	40.3	49.8
3rd Qu.	71.0	79.2
Max.	100.0	94.0

Those who scored under 50 were asked for their reasons for non-communication, those who scored 50 or above were asked for the reasons for communication.

Table 17 – Reasons for Non-communication, LE3b. [MC, R]

Reasons	RA (n=30)	RM (n=15)
Ensuring the independence of the risk assessment.	14	5
Other (please specify):	13	3
Organizational constraints.	7	2
Hierarchical constraints.	2	2
Limited time.	2	1
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	1	2
Risk manager unwilling to communicate.	1	
No trustful relationship with the risk manager		1

Table 18 – Reasons for Communication, LE3c. [MC, R],

Reasons	RA (n=39)	RM (n=23)
Keeping each other up to date.	24	9
Clarification of the questions in the mandate (from risk assessment OR by the risk manager)	20	9
Requesting additional information on the risk assessment mandate.	20	
Questions on the progress of the risk assessment.	16	10
Questions about the time schedule.	14	7
Giving further advice (e.g., management strategy).	7	
Other (please specify):	3	2
Giving additional information on the risk assessment mandate.		9
Receiving further advice (e.g., management strategy).		8

Moreover, the effectiveness of different communication channels was assessed (Table 19).

Table 19 - Effectiveness of communication channels, RA, LE7. (n=54) (Scale 1 "not effective at all" – 5 "very effective").

Channels	1	2	3	4	5
Official letter	7 (21.9%)	2 (6.2%)	9 (28.1%)	2 (6.2%)	12 (37.5%)
E-mail	0 (0.0%)	2 (4.0%)	8 (16.0%)	17 (34.0%)	23 (46.0%)
Telephone	1 (2.1%)	5 (10.4%)	8 (16.7%)	6 (12.5%)	28 (58.3%)
Video conference	5 (11.1%)	3 (6.7%)	6 (13.3%)	10 (22.2%)	21 (46.7%)
Face-to-Face conversation	2 (4.7%)	5 (11.6%)	2 (4.7%)	11 (25.6%)	23 (53.5%)

Chat and messenger service	13 (56.5%)	3 (13.0%)	4 (17.4%)	1 (4.3%)	2 (8.7%)
----------------------------	------------	-----------	-----------	----------	----------

Table 20 - Effectiveness of communication channels, RM, LE7. (n=31). (Scale 1 "not effective at all" – 5 "very effective").

Channels	1	2	3	4	5
Official letter	2 (9.5%)	2 (9.5%)	1 (4.8%)	2 (9.5%)	14 (66.7%)
E-mail	1 (3.6%)	1 (3.6%)	2 (7.1%)	9 (32.1%)	15 (53.6%)
Telephone	1 (3.8%)	1 (3.8%)	2 (7.7%)	5 (19.2%)	17 (65.4%)
Video conference	1 (4.0%)	2 (8.0%)	5 (20.0%)	7 (28.0%)	10 (40.0%)
Face-to-Face conversation	2 (8.3%)	2 (8.3%)	1 (4.2%)	8 (33.3%)	11 (45.8%)
Chat and messenger service	4 (28.6%)	3 (21.4%)	3 (21.4%)	2 (14.3%)	2 (14.3%)

The following two Tables provide information about the existence and importance of informal communication; with informal communication being defined as "all communication between risk assessor and risk managers that takes place outside of the predetermined processes in the risk analysis (e.g., a spontaneous phone call to clarify upcoming questions)."

Table 21 - Existence of informal communication, LE10a.

	Yes	No	I don't know / I prefer not to say.
RA	32	20	2
RM	18	10	3

Table 22 - Importance of informal communication, LE10b. [R]. RA (n=32) (Scale 1 do not agree at all– 5 agree completely).

Question	1	2	3	4	5
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Informal communication facilitated open communication between risk assessment and risk management.	3	0	23	23	52
Informal communication improved understanding of the mandate to the risk assessor.	17	3	17	13	50
Informal communication impaired the independence of the risk assessment process.	60	20	13	3	3
Informal communication improved the comprehensibility of the risk assessment.	10	7	24	21	38
Informal communication facilitated handing over the risk assessment to risk management.	14	14	21	21	31
Informal communication increased trust between risk assessment and risk management.	0	3	23	40	33

Table 23 - Importance of informal communication, LE10b, [R]. RM (n=18). (Scale 1 do not agree at all– 5 agree completely).

Question	1	2	3	4	5
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Informal communication facilitated open communication between risk assessment and risk management.	6	0	6	38	50
Informal communication improved understanding of the mandate to the risk management.	0	6	19	19	56
Informal communication impaired the independence of the risk management process.	38	31	6	6	19
Informal communication improved the comprehensibility of the risk management.	0	6	18	41	35

Informal communication facilitated handing over the risk assessment to risk management.	12	6	6	47	29
Informal communication increased trust between risk assessment and risk management.	0	0	12	53	35

Usefulness of risk assessment for risk management

The following Tables (24 and 25) cover how well the expectations of RM were met.

Table 24 – Correspondence between risk assessment report and risk management question (scale 1 not at all – 5 completely). RMLE12a, n=31.

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know / I prefer not to say
Match	0	0	5	15	5	6

Table 25 – Usefulness of risk assessment for risk management (scale 1 not at all useful – 5 very useful). RMLE13, n=31.

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know / I prefer not to say
Usefulness	0	1	4	10	15	1

Table 26 – Aspects, risk managers would like to have more information on, RMLE14 (n=31).

Aspects	Frequency
Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate.	3
Background information.	6
Details on the impact of different management scenarios.	11
Details on the methodology.	6
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	7
Other (please specify):	1

Other limitations of the risk assessment.	3
Raw data.	2
Recommendations for management strategies.	14
The results of the risk assessment.	7
Uncertainties in the risk assessment.	4

3.1.5 Reflections on the last risk analysis process

We explored if RA and RM know each other when working together and how important familiarity between RA and RM is for the risk analysis process.

Familiarity

Table 27 - Had you worked previously with RA / RM counterpart? LR3a

	Yes	No	I don't know / I prefer not to say.
RA	39	12	3
RM	19	10	2

Table 28 - Importance of familiarity (score 1 Not important at all – 5 Very important).
LR 3b

	1	2	3	4	5	I don't know / I prefer not to say
RA	8	7	13	6	5	0
RM	4	4	3	6	1	1

Role of trust

The following tables (including Table 35 in the outcome section) cover the question if trust in the risk analysis process is an important component.

Table 29 - Role of trust, LR5.

Role	RA (n=54)	RM (n=31)
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	8 (14.8%)	6 (19.3%)
It was crucial that all partners trusted each other.	32 (59.3%)	17 (54.8%)
It was not necessary that risk assessors and risk managers trusted each other.	10 (18.5%)	7 (22.6%)
Trust was only necessary between supervisory staff of risk assessment and risk management, not on a working level.	4 (7.4%)	1 (3.2%)

Feedback during and after the last risk analysis

Roughly half of RA and RM indicated that they received feedback from their counterpart on the last risk assessment mandate (See Table 30). When the feedback was received, the percentage of RM indicating that the feedback was good or very good was higher than this percentage of RA (See Table 31). RA indicated that they would mostly desire feedback on the usability of the risk assessment report in the risk management and on impact of the risk assessment on risk management (Table 32).

Table 30 – Feedback received, LR6a.

Feedback	RA (n=53)	RM (n=29)
No	23 (43.4%)	16 (55.2%)
Yes	30 (56.6%)	13 (44.8%)

Table 31 – Usefulness of the feedback (scale 1 very poor – 5 very good), LR6b

	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)
RA (n=30)	0	3.4	40.8	27.2	30.6
RM (n=13)	0	7.7	7.7	46.1	38.5

Table 32 - Desired feedback from the perspective of Risk Assessment, RALR7 (n=54).
[MC]

Desired Feedback	Frequency
Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate.	5
Background information.	4
Details on the impact of different management scenarios.	7
Details on the methodology.	4
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	6
Impact of the risk assessment on risk management.	27
Other (please specify):	5
Other limitations of the risk assessment.	8
Recommendations for management strategies.	9
The results of the risk assessment.	13
Uncertainties in the risk assessment.	8
Usability of the risk assessment report in risk management.	30

Outcome of the last risk analysis process

In general, the majority of the sample indicated that the quality of the risk analysis was good/very good for all the aspects, as the most frequent numbers marked by participants in the scale was 4 or 5. Nevertheless, time management seems to be the aspect with a lower quality in comparison with the others (See Table 33).

Table 33 – Quality of aspects in the last risk analysis (scale 1 very poor – 5 very good), LR1 [R].

Quality	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)
Work process (n=83)	2.4	4.8	20.5	35.0	37.3
Transparency amongst all involved partners (n=84)	2.4	6.0	14.3	32.1	45.2
Meeting risk analysis goals (effectiveness) (n=83)	2.4	3.6	15.7	45.8	32.5

Minimizing resource requirements (efficiency) (n=81)	4.9	6.2	24.7	40.7	23.5
Openness with risk management (assessment) (n=77)	2.6	5.2	15.6	35.0	41.6
Flexibility (n=78)	5.1	10.3	18.0	38.5	28.2
Time Management (n=83)	12.0	12.0	19.3	24.1	32.5
Timeliness (n=82)	3.7	14.6	17.1	25.6	39.0

RA and RM also seem to be satisfied regarding the communication with their counterparts. The most frequent numbers marked by participants in the scale were 4 or 5 (See Table 34).

Table 34 – Satisfaction with the communication between RA and RM (scale 1 not all satisfied – 5 very satisfied) (n=77), LR2.

	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)
Satisfaction	6.5	3.9	15.6	26.0	48.0

Relationship / Trust

We defined trust as the willingness of an entity (the trustor) to become vulnerable to another entity (i.e., the trustee) based on the presumption that the trustee is trustworthy. Trustworthiness we defined as being determined by perceptions about the trustee's ability and the belief that the trustee acts in line with the trustor's interests (Schilke et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 1995).

Please note that item 1 (familiarity) was phrased negatively. For the results section and further analysis, the values are presented inverted. Items are paraphrased. See RALR4 & RMLR4 for the original set of questions.

Table 35 – Relationship / Trust (scale 1 do not agree at all– 5 agree completely), LR4 [R].

Relationship / Trust	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)
Familiarity (n=70)	22.9	18.6	15.7	10.0	32.9

Vulnerability_a (n=73)	6.8	6.8	11.0	21.9	53.4
Vulnerability_b (n=70)	5.7	4.3	21.4	25.7	42.9
Vulnerability_c (n=66)	7.6	7.6	16.7	25.8	42.4
Feeling valued (n=71)	9.9	4.2	14.1	29.6	42.3
Ability (n=71)	1.4	2.8	22.5	26.8	46.5
Interest alignment (n=63)	7.9	7.9	22.2	25.4	36.5

3.1.6 Challenges of risk analysis

Table 36 provides an overview over the frequency of occurrence of defined challenges during risk analysis.

Table 36 – Communication challenges (scale 1 never 2 rarely 3 sometimes 4 often 5 always), CII.

Challenges	1(%)	2(%)	3(%)	4(%)	5(%)
If I couldn't reach my previous contact person, I didn't know who to approach. (n=87)	41.4	35.6	14.9	4.6	3.4
If I needed additional expertise, I didn't know how to find the right person to talk to. (n=89)	37.1	29.2	22.5	9.0	2.2
If I was absent at short notice (e.g., due to illness), there was no one who could answer questions about my work. (n=85)	28.2	30.6	30.6	9.4	1.2
There was not enough time to resolve disagreements. (n=86)	34.9	30.2	17.4	14.0	3.5
Procedural constraints hindered open communication with my risk analysis counterpart. (n=89)	39.3	29.2	19.1	9.0	3.4

3.2 Chi-squares and Kruskal-Wallis H tests

As explained in section 2.4, we used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between RA and RM for a set of variables. There is no significant difference between RA and RM regarding the length of the last risk process ($p > 0.05$). However, there is a significant difference between RA and RM regarding autonomy in the last risk analysis: $X^2(1, N = 81) = 14.685, p = .0001$. RA are more likely than RM to perceive their work as fully autonomous.

We also used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between those who shared resources and those who did not share resources for satisfaction with communication and for quality aspects of risk analysis. There are no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Finally, we used the Chi-Square test of independence to determine differences between those who received feedback and those who did not receive it in the last risk analysis for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. There are no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

We used the Kruskal-Wallis H test to determine differences among RA, RM, and those who do both for satisfaction with communication, and quality aspects of risk analysis. There are no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

We also used the Kruskal-Wallis H test to determine differences among participants working in organizations providing risk assessment, providing risk management, and providing both for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. There are no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). Finally, we used the Kruskal-Wallis H to determine differences between those that indicated that trust was not necessary on the last risk analysis and those who indicated that trust was crucial, and those who indicated that trust was only necessary at a higher level, not at a working level for the following variables: satisfaction with communication and quality aspects of risk analysis. There are no significant differences ($p > 0.05$).

3.3 Correlations

Several correlations of relevant variables and outcome measures were calculated. Only moderate (> 0.3) and large (> 0.5) effect sizes are presented below.

Table 37 – Length of risk assessment with outcome variables.

Outcome	Spearman's r	p
Satisfaction with communication	-0.29	<0.05
Quality of risk analysis	-0.38	<0.05
Relationship / Trust	-0.19	<0.05

Table 38 – Correlation (Spearman's r) matrix of outcome variables.

	Satisfaction	Quality	Relationship / Trust
Satisfaction with communication	1	0.71	0.62
Quality of risk analysis	0.71	1	0.56
Relationship / Trust	0.62	0.56	1

4. Interpretation and concluding comments

The aim of the ENCOMRAN project is to provide recommendations to enhance the communication and overall interaction between RA and RM, thus facilitating the risk analysis process regarding food and feed hazards. To support this aim, an online questionnaire was created and distributed among RA and RM working at authorities/governmental organizations in European countries. We were particularly interested in exploring the collected data to provide insights regarding RA and RM satisfaction in communication and overall interaction in the last risk analysis, their perceptions of quality aspects in their last risk analysis and the (trust) relationship between each other. We were also interested in the challenges they faced in communication. Key findings are further discussed below.

Results indicated that the vast majority of RA and RM are quite satisfied with their communication. The majority do not frequently face challenges, such as procedural constraints or not finding a contact person or an additional expert, if needed. In general, most RA and RM indicated that the quality aspect in the last risk analysis was good/very good for the work process, the transparency amongst partners, meeting risk analysis goals (effectiveness), minimizing resource requirements (efficiency), openness with risk management (assessment), flexibility, timeliness and time management. Most of the respondents indicated that it was crucial that all partners trusted each other. However, a

smaller part of our sample indicated that they were not satisfied with the communication in the last risk analysis and some quality aspects were perceived less positively. For example, 24% perceived the time management of the last risk analysis as rather poor, 41,2% stated they would sometimes to always struggle with being replaced in case of absence and 34,9% with finding enough time to resolve disagreements. These results encourage us to explore deeper which factors could explain satisfaction, quality and trust.

Our first approach was to explore differences in satisfaction with communication and quality in the last risk analysis among groups. We tested differences among the following groups: those who share resources and those who do not share resources; RA, RM, and those who do both; those working in organizations providing risk assessment, providing risk management, and providing both. Results, however, showed that there were no significant differences among these groups regarding satisfaction with communication and quality in the last risk analysis. This is a key finding: grouping respondents based on an external characteristic (e.g., access to a shared resource, or type of working organization) seems insufficient to detect differences among groups in satisfaction with communication and quality in the last risk analysis. We also explored for differences between those that indicated that trust was not necessary on the last risk analysis and those who indicated that trust was crucial, and those who indicated that trust was only necessary at a higher level, not at a working level, but results were not significant.

We then moved to our second approach: to understand the relations among satisfaction, quality, and relationship / trust. The key finding is the large positive correlations among these variables, indicating that the higher the perceptions of quality in the last risk analysis, and the better the relationship between RA and RM, the higher the satisfaction with the communication in the last risk analysis. Although causality cannot be demonstrated, these results suggested that risk analysis quality and trust played an important role in the general satisfaction with communication and vice versa. We further explore the role of the length of the last risk analysis in satisfaction, quality, and relationship / trust. Not surprisingly, the key finding is the negative correlations among length and the outcome variables, indicating that the more time a risk analysis takes, the lower the satisfaction with communication, the lower the perceptions of quality in the risk analysis, and the worse the relationship between RA and RM.

Our central findings stemming from descriptive statistics are provided below.

General findings

The risk analysis process usually takes less than 6 months. The duration of the risk analysis process is influenced by the category of the last risk analysis (e.g., routine risk assessment usually takes more time).

The questions regarding the autonomy during the last risk analysis produced different results for RA and RM. While 72% of Risk Assessors perceived their last risk assessment as performed fully autonomous, the view of RM on autonomy was more diverse: 34% of Risk Managers stated that another entity coordinated the risk analysis process, 24% stated that they worked jointly with RA and 24% reviewed their work during last risk analysis as fully autonomous. These differences in perception of the same risk analysis process are worth further investigation. It reflects the somewhat ambivalent state of interaction that is further supported when looking at areas where risk managers would like further exchange on and the reasons for non-communication. When asked which aspects risk managers would like more information on from risk assessors, impact of different management scenarios and recommendations for management strategies were the most frequently mentioned. 35% of those risk assessors who reported to not communicate frequently, gave “ensuring the independence of the risk assessment” as a reason. These results suggest that the emphasis on autonomy restraints, at least in some instances, the interaction between assessors and managers. It could also explain the different viewpoints on autonomy across risk assessors and risk managers. These findings support the call from the General Food Law (EC/178/2002) “in order to promote coherence between the risk assessment, risk management and risk communication functions, the link between risk assessors and risk managers should be strengthened.”

Findings regarding the execution of risk analysis

RM perceived the frequency of communication with RA higher than RA with RM. The mean of frequency of communication on a scale from -1 to 100 for RA and RM together was slightly below 50.

Informal communication was perceived as preferable to facilitate open communication (~50% RA and RM agree completely) and to improve the understanding of the mandate (~50% RA and RM agree completely). But at the same time a considerable amount of RA and RM personnel had no informal communication. Interestingly, RM perceives official letters as most effective for communication with

RA, while RA finds phone calls most effective. Further studies how open and informal forms of communication may improve risk analysis are needed.

Findings regarding the reflection on risk analysis

Feedback is not always provided, but when provided people tend to believe it is useful. In terms of familiarity between RA and RM it is noteworthy, that most respondents knew and had previously worked with the RA / RM contact person before. At the same time the question regarding the importance of familiarity between RA and RM does produce quite heterogeneous distribution ranging from very important to not important at all.

Conclusion

Based on our EU-wide sample, we conclude that the interaction between RA and RM can be considered effective in terms of satisfaction in communication between RA and RM and perceived quality of risk analysis process. Our recommendations to improve the interaction between RA and RM match many COMRISK recommendations, which are to organize networking activities and enhance frequent communication between RA and RM to improve their relationship. However, more in depth studies on the role of trust and how to facilitate it are needed.

Moreover, we encourage the establishment of informal communication channels and recommend the integration of feedback loops within the risk analysis process as feedback was not provided on a regular basis in all cases but receiving feedback was often perceived as useful.

On a broader level, we propose for risk managers, risk assessors and other relevant actors to reflect on the tension between ensuring autonomy and enabling effective interaction.

References

Andersson, M. G., Elving, J., Nordkvist, E., Urdl, M., Engblom, L., Mader, A., Altmeyer, S., Kowalczyk, J., Lahrssen-Wiederholt, M., Tuominen, P., Joutsen, S., Suomi, J., Mikkela, A., Hinkka, N., Siekkinen, K.-M., van der Fels-Klerx, H.J., van den Borne, B., Ali, B (2020). Communication inside Risk Assessment and Risk

Management (COMRISK): Final report, *EFSA Supporting publication 17(7)*, 1891E.
doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1891

IRGC (2017). *Introduction to the IRGC Risk Governance Framework, revised version*.
EPFL International Risk Governance Center. doi:10.5075/epfl-irgc-233739

McNamara, M. (2012). Starting to Untangle the Web of Cooperation, Coordination, and
Collaboration: A Framework for Public Managers, *International Journal of Public
Administration*, 35(6), 389-401. doi:10.1080/01900692.2012.655527

Mayer, R. C., Davis, J. H., & Schoorman, F. D. (1995). An Integrative Model of
Organizational Trust. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 709–734.
doi:10.2307/258792

Schilke, O., Reimann, M., & Cook, K. S. (2021). Trust in Social Relations. *Annual
Review of Sociology*, 47(1), 239–259. doi:10.1146/annurev-soc-082120-082850

Appendix

A: Insights into type “Both”

Within which subject area did you prepare the last risk analysis?

Subject Area	Frequency
Biological hazards in food.	4
Chemical hazards in feed.	1
Chemical hazards in food.	4
Other (please specify):	3
Physical hazards in food.	2

How long did the last risk analysis process take?

Length	Frequency
Four to six months.	3
Less than a month.	3
One to three months.	2

Which tasks were you involved in during your last risk analysis?

Tasks	Frequency
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	2

Compiling risk profiles.	2
Controlling the implemented options.	1
Determining how to assess the risk.	4
Evaluating the implemented options.	2
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	2
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	1
Hazard characterization.	1
Hazard identification.	5
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	2
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	1
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	3
Planning options to deal with the risk.	3
Problem framing.	2
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	1
Risk characterization.	3
Risk communication.	2
Screening and early warning.	1
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	2
Stakeholder engagement.	2

Would you have preferred that certain tasks of the last risk analysis process would have been performed by separate entities?

Opinion	Frequency
No	5
Yes	3

Which of the following tasks should be performed separately?

Tasks	Frequency
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	1
Determining how to assess the risk.	2
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	1
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	1
Planning options to deal with the risk.	1

Problem framing.	1
------------------	---

What kind of information was included in the last risk assessment mandate?

Mandate	Frequency
A description of the circumstance that gave rise to the enquiry.	5
A description of the risk to be assessed.	4
Information on different risk management strategies pertaining to this risk.	3
The intended use of the risk assessment.	2
